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Thiocyanato and Cyanato Complexes of Copper(II) and Nickel(II) with 1,3-Diaminopropane-2-ol, $H_2NCH_2CH(OH)CH_2NH_2$

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IN recent years much interest has been shown on the transition metal complexes of ambidentate ligands. Owing to its ambidentate nature, the pseudohalides and host of other ligands of similar properties, can show the phenomena of linkage isomerisms in coordination complexes.¹ In this note we describe the preparation and properties of some thiocyanato- and cyanato complexes of nickel(II) and copper(II) with 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol (= L). This work is an extension of our previous study on the coordination complexes of copper(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) salts (including pseudohalides) with neutral Schiff bases^{2,3} and pyrazoles.⁴

Experimental

(All the preparations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere).

$Cu(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (I): An ethanolic solution of cupric nitrate trihydrate (0.005 mole) was refluxed for 15 min in presence of 20 ml of 2,2-dimethoxypropane. To this refluxed solution was then added L (0.01 mole) in 10 ml of ethanol, followed by the addition of solid ammonium thiocyanate (0.01 mole). The whole mixture was then refluxed for 10 min, and the dark blue solution was filtered. The filtrate on slow evaporation in a vacuum desiccator yielded blue crystals. These were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol, ether and then dried in a desiccator over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

The complex is soluble in pyridine, dimethylsulfoxide and dimethylformamide. The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.90$ B.M. at 29°). Found: SCN, 32.06; Cu, 17.85%. Calc. for $C_8H_{20}N_6O_2S_2Cu$: SCN, 32.27; Cu, 17.66%.

$Cu(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (II): Analogous method by using potassium cyanate instead of ammonium thiocyanate yielded this bluish green crystals.

The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.88$ B.M. at 28°). Found: N, 25.14; Cu, 19.71%. Calc. for $C_8H_{20}N_6O_4Cu$: N, 25.65; Cu, 19.39%.

$Ni(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (III): Following the method of analogous copper(II) complexes and using nickel nitrate hexahydrate instead of copper(II) nitrate trihydrate, this pale green complex was isolated.

It is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 3.22$ B.M. at 28°). Found: SCN, 32.19; Ni, 16.14%. Calc. for $C_8H_{20}N_6O_2S_2Ni$: SCN, 32.68; Ni, 16.63%.

$Ni(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (IV): Following the method used for corresponding copper(II) complex, this pale green complex was isolated.

It is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 3.35$ B.M. at 28°). Found: N, 25.71; Ni, 18.02%. Calc. for $C_8H_{20}N_6O_4Ni$: N, 26.01; Ni, 18.27%.

Results and Discussion

The copper(II) complexes $Cu(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (I) and $Cu(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (II) are sufficiently stable to handle in the atmospheric conditions. These two complexes are highly soluble in pyridine and DMSO, and in the latter solvent they are found to be virtually non-conducting (Λ_M varies between 2.8–3.5 mhos of a $\times 10^{-3}M$ solution at room temperature). The magnetic moments are calculated to be 1.90 and 1.88 B.M. (room temperature) respectively, which suggest the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for a d^9 system. The i.r. spectral data (Table) support that the anions SCN and NCO are coordinated to the metal ion, which is in conformity with the non-conducting nature of the chelates.

The i.r. spectra of the two copper complexes exhibit two bands at 2080 cm^{-1} (s) and 720 cm^{-1} (m) in the regions of ν_{C-N} and ν_{C-S} vibrations respectively, which is diagnostic for S-bonded SCN ligand.⁵ It has been suggested by Tramer⁶ that on coordination, the high frequency $C \equiv N$ stretching mode is raised by $\sim 30-40$ cm^{-1} , $\sim 50-70$ cm^{-1} and 70–120 cm^{-1} over the ν_{C-N} band observed at 1963 cm^{-1} for the ionic thiocyanate group indicating terminal N- and S- and bridging thiocyanate group respectively. However, the ν_{C-S} stretching frequency which drops in S-bonded thiocyanate complexes⁷ relative to that in KSCN, (ν_{C-S} at 749 cm^{-1}) can be a more useful guide to the mode of thiocyanate bonding. In the present case, its occurrence at 720 cm^{-1} clearly indicates the S-bonding.

TABLE—INFRARED AND VISIBLE ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA (CM^{-1}) OF CU(II) AND NI(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	ν_{C-N}	ν_{C-S}	ν_{C-O}	ν_{max} (nujol mull)
$Cu(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (I)	2080(s)	720(m)	—	16,600
$Cu(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (II)	2135(s)	—	1338(m)	16,800
$Ni(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (III)	2078(s)	730(m)	—	10,850; 12,850(sh); 16,950.
$Ni(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (IV)	2130(m)	—	1330(m)	10,500; 13,000(sh); 16,800.

The cyanate complex of copper(II) shows bands at 2135 cm^{-1} and 1338 cm^{-1} , assignable to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ vibrations. It has been demonstrated⁸ that for N-bonded NCO group, the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ appears at 1300 cm^{-1} and for O-bonded NCO group it occurs at a much lower frequency (below 1200 cm^{-1}). It is therefore concluded that in the present copper(II) chelate the NCO group is N-bonded to the metal ion as $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ appears to absorb at 1338 cm^{-1} . The electronic spectra (nujol mull) (Table) of thiocyanato and cyanato complexes of copper(II) shows band $\sim 17,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ —indicating the presence of highly distorted octahedral ligand arrangement around copper(II) ion.

The i.r. spectral data of nickel(II) complexes (Table) suggest S-bonded SCN and N-bonded NCO ligand to be present in (III) and (IV) respectively. The magnetic moment values (see experimental) and the electronic absorption spectral data (Table) suggest distorted octahedral geometry for the chelates.

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New Compounds of Chromium(V) : Tetraphenylarsonium and Tetraphenylphosphonium Oxotetrachloro-Chromate(V)

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CHROMIUM(V) is well known in the form of oxotetra- and penta chloro-chromate(V) discovered by Weinland and coworkers¹ to which important

additions were made by others². All of them, as are known, are sensitive to moisture, mildheat, light and storage.

Here we report the preparations and properties of two new compounds in the series which unlike those known, are stable and are obtained from chromyl chloride.

Oxotetrachloro chromate(V) salts of tetraphenylarsonium(I) and tetraphenylphosphonium(II) cations, $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{As}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$ and $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{P}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$ were isolated by reducing chromyl chloride taken in pure acetic acid by dry HCl gas at 0° in the dark condition and precipitating the compounds(I) and (II) with tetraphenylarsonium chloride and tetraphenylphosphonium chloride dissolved in pure acetic acid respectively. The precipitates were filtered in sintered glass gooch crucibles, washed with acetic acid and finally with benzene and dried over concentrated sulphuric acid.

Yields were nearly quantitative. Analytical results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1				
	Cr	Cl	A	O.S.
Found % for (I)	8.80	25.24	10.98	5.06
Calc. % for (I)	8.77	23.94	12.65	5.00
Found % for (II)	9.73	25.23	4.94	4.87
Calc. % for (II)	9.47	25.86	5.64	5.00

A = As in (I) and P in (II), O.S. = Oxidation State.

These compounds are light buff in color and similar in properties and resemble in formula and other properties those in the series having large heterocyclic nitrogen bases acting as cations.

The compound(I) begins to incinerate at 193° and melts at 200° and (II) does the same things at 205° and 228° respectively.

(I) is soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, nitrobenzene, nitromethane, dimethylformamide, but insoluble in water, acetic acid, benzene, carbontetrachloride. (II) has similar solubility, but apparently slightly more than (I).

Λ_0 in nitromethane at 22° is 87.68 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2/\text{mole}$ for (I) and 87.14 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2/\text{mole}$ for (II) indicating them to be 1 : 1 electrolytes.³

The magnetic susceptibility was measured at 23° and the corrected magnetic moments were found to be 1.65 B.M. for (I) and 1.72 B.M. for (II) indicating that these contained d^1 systems which substantiate the chemical evidence.

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